

Comparative Analysis of Low-Cost and High-Cost Building Using Civil Engineering Software's Simulation and Material Optimization

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Abstract- This research analyses and compares the structural and financial viability of low-cost versus high-cost housing designs for a G+4 residential building using civil engineering software's. Emphasis is placed on load analysis, material selection (including Fe415/Fe500 steel and fly ash bricks), and structural optimization following Indian Standard codes. Results show that a cost-efficient approach reduces expenses significantly and maintains safety, performance, and sustainability. This research aims to analyze and compare the material aspects of high-cost and low-cost buildings. The study investigates the use of different materials, their properties, and their impact on the overall cost and sustainability of the structures. The research methodology involves a comprehensive literature review, case studies of existing high-cost and low-cost buildings, and a comparative analysis of material costs, durability, environmental impact, and aesthetic considerations.

Keywords- Low-cost housing, High-cost housing, Structural analysis, Material selection, Fe415/Fe500 steel, Fly ash bricks

I. INTRODUCTION

Affordable housing is critical in urban planning, especially for rapidly growing cities. This study evaluates a G+4 residential structure (104' x 71'7") by implementing both low-cost and high-cost construction methods, and assessing their implications on structure, cost, labour, and sustainability.

Low- and high-cost buildings are determined by purpose, budget, and expectations. A building size of 104' x 71'7" may either be designed as one or the other based on the requirements of the end-user. Optimal application of engineering and design software such as STAAD Pro for structural analysis, AutoCAD for drawing, Revit for BIM, and estimation software for costing control ensures that both types meet safety criteria and function as needed. While

low-cost buildings emphasize price and quick construction time, high-cost buildings emphasize luxury, durability, and integration of technology both of which are possible with proper application of contemporary construction software and planning.

II. METHODOLOGY

1. Software and Simulation

STAAD.Pro V8i (SELECT series 6) was employed for structural load analysis. The simulation included:

- 257 nodes, 549 beams, and 5 plates.
- Load types: seismic (X and Z), wind loads ($\pm X$, $\pm Z$), live load, and dead load.
- Combination load cases such as DL + 0.25LL were analyzed.

2. Material Specification

The low-cost model incorporated:

- M25 grade concrete
 - AAC and fly ash bricks
 - Fe415 steel
 - Local materials and simplified finishes
- The high-cost model used:
- Premium finish materials
 - Fe500 steel
 - Higher reinforcement density and cost-intensive features.

3. BBS and Reinforcement

Bar Bending Schedule (BBS) was created for each slab segment. Steel consumption ranged:

- S1 slab area: ~8,713 kg including 5% wastage
- S3 slab area: ~993 kg for 2 merged zones

The BBS presents the total reinforcement requirements for a G+4 low-cost building, designed using Fe415 and Fe500 steel with M15 and M25 concrete. The purpose is precise cutting, bending, and fixing of steel bars while reducing waste and improving material cost estimation and site logistics. It includes reinforcement details for slabs, beams, columns, footings, and staircases.

Key Values Extracted

Column stirrups (12"x12")

- Length: 594.88 m
- Weight: 235.01 kg

Column stirrups (15"x15")

- Length: 9470.91 m
- Weight: 3741.59 kg

Roof Beam-2

- Length: 89.78 m
- Weight: 35.47 kg
- Additional roof beam steel: 82 m, 130 kg

Staircase (2 flights)

- Flight X-X total weight: 97.502 kg
- Flight Y-Y total weight: 93.953 kg

Other components (e.g., stirrups, extra bars) span several more entries, but overall steel reinforcement

quantities are detailed precisely for all key elements.

III. DESIGN PARAMETERS

1. Structural Design

The RCC-framed structure was modelled to balance strength, serviceability, and cost-effectiveness. Slabs were designed as two-way slabs supported on edge beams. Bracing and shear walls ensured lateral stability.

Fig. 3.1

2. Code Compliance

IS codes followed include:

- IS 456:2000 (Concrete)
- IS 875 (Load considerations)
- IS 1893:2016 (Seismic design)
- IS 2185 (AAC & fly ash blocks)
- IS 10262:2019 (Concrete mix design)

IV. ESTIMATION AND COSTING

1. Material Quantity and Cost

Materials like bricks, steel, concrete, and finishes were quantified and priced using CPWD/local market rates. The cost per square foot was computed for both models, clearly highlighting the cost-effectiveness of the low-cost model.

2. Comparison Criteria

Models were evaluated across:

- Structural performance
- Environmental impact
- Construction time
- Labour intensity
- Cost per unit area

V. TOTAL CONSTRUCTION COST SUMMARY

The estimated cost of the entire G+4 building is structured into core construction and interior design costs:

- Base Building Cost (G+4): ₹23,250,560.44
- Interior Design (2BHK & 3BHK): ₹15,200,000.00
- Grand Total (with interiors): ₹38,450,560.44

TOTAL AMOUNT IN SUPER-STRUCTURE WORK (Rs.)	5992597.1
TOTAL AMOUNT IN SUB-STRUCTURE WORK (Rs.)	1672078.762
TOTAL AMOUNT (Rs.)	7664675.862

Fig. 5.1

Breakdown of Major Components

- Concrete Framework: ₹7,664,675.86
- Total Steel: ₹7,276,055
- 9" AAC Block Wall: ₹1,159,896.68
- 4" Red Brick Wall: ₹1,401,351.77
- Flooring Work: ₹1,320,556.02
- Stainless Steel Railing: ₹1,775,822.4
- Plaster Work: ₹1,180,869.05
- Painting Work: ₹371,824.19
- PVC Panels: ₹85,911.33
- Aluminium Doors/Windows: ₹625,998.15
- Doors, Windows & Ventilation: ₹387,600

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- **Safety:** Both models met safety norms, with adequate design for lateral forces.
- **Cost:** The low-cost model reduced total material expenditure by over 30%.
- **Labour:** Labour was optimized via simpler material handling and layout.
- **Sustainability:** The use of fly ash and AAC bricks reduced the carbon footprint.
- **Time:** Faster execution due to easier materials and reduced complexity.

Table 7.1

Category	Low-Cost Model	High-Cost Model
Structure Type	G+4 RCC Framed	G+4 RCC Framed
Concrete Grade	M25	M25
Steel Type	Fe415	Fe500
Bricks Used	AAC/Fly Ash	Clay/High-Cost Bricks
STAAD Nodes	257	257
Beams	549	549
Plates	5	5
Steel (S1 Slab)	~8,713 kg	Higher (due Fe500)
Environmental Impact	Lower (fly ash, local material)	Higher (premium materials)
Seismic/Wind Load	Considered	Considered
Cost Efficiency	~30% lower	High cost
Execution Time	Faster	Slower
IS Code Compliance	Yes (IS 456, 875, 1893, 2185)	Same codes
Labour Requirements	Optimized	Labour intensive
Sustainability	High	Low

VII. CONCLUSION

The low-cost construction model delivers a structurally sound, environmentally friendly, and financially viable solution without compromising safety or comfort. Strategic design using cost-effective materials and adherence to IS codes proves critical in addressing the urban housing crisis affordably.

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